

ISSN 2181-8622

Manufacturing technology problems

**Scientific and Technical Journal
Namangan Institute of
Engineering and Technology**

**Volume 8
Issue 1
2023**

subsidies and grants for them, benefits and it will be appropriate to provide preferences, as well as provide constant advisory support.

It is also important to take measures to inform the public and business circles about the benefits of social entrepreneurship.

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LEGAL REGULATION OF ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITY

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Abstract:

Objective. The Economic Association of Interaction - individuals or legal entities, in order to combine the wines to maintain their independence, and the combined facilities. Corporation - for, to work in partnership to achieve common goals, united, independent legal entity - a legal person, the person described in the amount of medication. They are created in the form of joint stock companies. The concentration of enterprises is carried out in the form of cartel, syndicate, holding and financial-industrial groups.

Methods. In the process of analysis, methods of comparison and systematic analysis were used. The state of ensuring the development of sustainable development was assessed by the monitoring method and the corresponding conclusions were formed through abstract-logical thinking.

Results. The selection of the best forms of communication between the factors under consideration plays an important role in the effective modeling of data on the processes of ensuring the security of small business and private entrepreneurship by methods of correlation-regression analysis. In this article, we give examples of a system of normal equations generated by the least squares method to determine the mathematical models often used and the unknown parameters in the models and its application in practice.

Conclusion. The concept of security should firstly, meet the environmental goals and objectives of the enterprise and secondly, to consider external effects on the environment that may have a direct or indirect impact on the safety of the enterprise. At the same time, the company's work is critical for some measures to ensure the safety of the accused should be done, and, above all, for the appropriate reserve should confirm the creation order.

Keywords: production, goods, working capital, fixed assets, national economy, funds, economic activity, economic stability, quality enterprise, business, method, mathematical model, economic security, coefficient of variation, confidence interval.

Introduction.

The Economic Association of Interaction - individuals or legal entities, in order to combine the wines to maintain their independence, and the combined facilities. Corporation - for, to work in partnership to achieve common goals, united, independent legal entity - a legal person, the person described in the amount of medication. They are created in the form of joint stock companies. The concentration of enterprises is carried out in the form of cartel, syndicate, holding and financial-industrial groups. Schedule of production problems in the production of characters, prices, sales of goods, labor issues, such as recruitment and acts on the basis of the contract. In this form of integration, enterprises are united on the basis of cooperation, while maintaining their independence. Syndicate of commercial activity (supply, sale, and pay the price to do), which will be organized on the basis of the association is. Within the framework of the syndicate, enterprises retain their legal and economic status. Trest are highly centralized. His enterprises lose production, trade and independence and operate according to a single plan. Holdings are an effective form of management that allows you to consolidate and coordinate the financial

resources of participants, as well as quickly perform production tasks.

These enterprises will be engaged in integration processes in order to:

- Achieving a more efficient use of resources;
- Updating and strengthening cooperation through cooperation;
- Access of entrepreneurs to foreign markets;
- Attracting new types of investment in production;
- Pursuing a unified pricing and sales policy to achieve success in the domestic and foreign markets.

Methods. In the process of analysis, methods of comparison and systematic analysis were used. The state of ensuring the development of sustainable development was assessed by the monitoring method and the corresponding conclusions were formed through abstract-logical thinking.

Results. N.V. Matveev offers the following definition of economic security of an enterprise: "this is the state of the enterprise, which ensures the stability of its functioning, financial equilibrium and regular profit-making, the ability to fulfill set goals and objectives, and the ability to further develop and improve".

Alshanskaya T.V., Kazhaeva Yu.D. and Mironenko A.V. offer a classification of security threats that can

small business and private entrepreneurship, their equal opportunities in competition and economic security.

The mathematical model $u = a_0 + a_1x_1 + a_2x_2 + a_3x_3 + a_4x_4 + a_5x_5 + a_6x_6 + a_7x_7$, was sought in the form. Here, it is the gross domestic product (billion soums); x_1 - industry (billion soums), x_2 - construction (billion soums); x_3 -, employment (thousand people); x_4 – export (mln.USH.dol); x_5 - import (mln. USD); x_6 - trade (billion soums); x_7 - agriculture, forestry and fisheries (billion soums), $a_0, a_1, \dots, a_7$ - constant numbers. To find the coefficients $a_0, a_1, \dots, a_7$ we use the method of least squares of mathematical statistics. As a result, we create the following mathematical model.

$$y = 1174,46 + 184,84 x_1 + 78,45 x_2 + 79,7 x_3 + 17,9 x_4 + 37,41 x_5 + 299,45 x_6 + 47,7 x_7.$$

The analysis of the mathematical model shows that the influence of industry, trade, agriculture, forestry and fisheries on the factors shaping the potential of the gross domestic product is significant.

Institutional reforms in the oil and gas sector of the country Creation of “Uzbekneftegaz”, structural and substantial change in vertically integrated structures in the direction of market relations.[1] Transformation of the state concern into the national corporation Uzbekneftegaz [2] from the creation of NHC "Uzbekneftegaz" It is characterized by a three-stage process consisting of.[3] Of course, as a result of these organizational changes, some enterprises were liquidated, while others received new institutional names. Entered into the existing system of the Company on August 21, 2006.

Discussions. Determining the level of public-legal regulation of business is a very delicate matter. For example, protecting the domestic market is a constant and necessary task for every state. However, the other side of the issue is the extent to which customs restrictions are imposed in order to protect the domestic market.

In particular, a number of countries have imposed trade embargoes on basic foodstuffs. In addition, the activities of businesses related to the provision of services within the country have been suspended. The analysis shows that in times of crisis, there are sharp changes in the trajectory of the dynamics of public regulation of entrepreneurial activity. This will increase the mass influence of the state in a number of sectors of the economy, and thus stabilize the private economy with the help of the state. With the stabilization of economic relations, the influence of the state on the economy is reduced, and in the regulation of economic relations, public law begins to give way to private law, and, of course, this changes the dynamics of public regulation of the economy.[4]

The policy of the state to determine the level and dynamics of public regulation of entrepreneurial activity can be compared to a passenger on horseback. The passenger pulls the reins of the horse slightly on uneven, high and low parts of the road (otherwise, he may fall) and when he goes out on a flat road, he loosens the reins of the horse again. But he never let go of the horse's bridle completely. Because in case of emergencies and other dangers, it will be necessary to

control the horse in a safe direction immediately.

1-fig. The need for mass legal regulation of entrepreneurial activity

Similarly, in times of crisis and depression and transition, the public influence of the state on entrepreneurial activity is increased, but as the economic processes stabilize, the public influence of the state on entrepreneurial activity is reduced. But entrepreneurial activity cannot be completely exempt from the imperative influence of the state. The study and research of the level and dynamics of mass legal regulation of entrepreneurial activity, the development of proposals and recommendations in this regard is important for the liberalization of relations between the state and the business entity. at the same time, it plays an important role in shaping a modern democratic market economy by maintaining the appropriate influence of the state in business, ensuring the

harmony and balance of public and private interests in the relationship between the state and the business entity. Thus, in the context of the coronavirus pandemic and the global crisis, there have been significant changes in the level and dynamics of public regulation of business in countries around the world, including Uzbekistan. In particular, in Uzbekistan during this period there was an increase in the dynamics of public regulation of entrepreneurial activity on some issues, and on some issues the opposite, and thus the state provided a reasonable public-legal influence on entrepreneurial activity on the basis of "manual management".

Conclusion. The concept of security should firstly, meet the environmental goals and objectives

of the enterprise and secondly, to consider external effects on the environment that may have a direct or indirect impact on the safety of the enterprise. At the same time, the company's work is critical for some measures to ensure the safety of the accused should be done, and, above all, for the appropriate reserve should confirm the creation order. The experience of domestic and foreign practice identifies the following areas of activity:

1. Ensure the protection of buildings and structures, communications and equipment.

2. Fast, confidential information and the safety management body, passengers and cargo traffic control, investigate violations, security information security.

3. Ensure the safety of the administrative officer (workers) in the preparation and training, inspection, audit and measures to prevent rat problems, promising to develop.

4. Protection of material resources and disaster management, fire protection, fire safety and monitoring the status of fire alarm systems, etc.

Company managers must report on the results of continuous labor safety. Only when necessary can security measures be kept confidential. Confidentiality of security measures requires the establishment of special supervision over the application and observance of business rules by business units.

The charter of the Security Service of the enterprise determines its goals and objectives, rights and obligations, control and audit activities. The security service operates on the basis of a high

level of security and enterprise support, which includes:

- Organization of confidential events;
- Ensuring information security;
- Engineering and technical protection;
- Measures to prevent negative trends in the workforce.

The company to ensure the safety of its economic indicators, to improve their behavior. This will increase the image of the enterprise. It serves the welfare of society and society.

The trade secrets of the enterprise are related to production, technological information, management, finance and so on. Corporate trade secrets The BBC category features as defined by law.

According to current prospects, business secrets of an enterprise usually include the following:

- Trade relations of the enterprise;
- Capital structure and structure, investment plans;
- Suppliers and customers, contracts;
- Production volume, working capital and profit;
- Assessment of policies and the price of the goods constitute a means of livelihood;
- Banking operations, etc.

In addition to the term "trade secret", the term "trade secret" is also used. It includes information on production methods, technologies, technical inventions, research, labor organization, communications and so on.

Disclosure of today's market relations, especially from the point of view of competitive confidentiality of business and production secrets of the

enterprise, can negatively affect its condition and lead to the loss of consumers of products. According to experts, the loss of a quarter of business data is also an excellent opportunity for competitors, and half of the companies that published the data within a few months may go bankrupt. For this reason, it is advisable to establish a clear legal status and classification of trade secrets and develop a mechanism of responsibility for their disclosure.

Accurate calculation of the total amount of losses is a complex and time-consuming process, and sometimes it is impossible to calculate due to the lack of reliable data. The above requires additional costs from enterprises and reduces their productivity and competitiveness. That is why much attention is now being paid to protecting trade secrets.

Economic security is based on the following principles:

Firstly, it is the freedom to choose activities and forms. Although a “market

economy” is a multidimensional concept, its main feature is the freedom of economic activity.

Of course, economic freedom is limited to circles that do not allow it to enter into anarchy and economic independence. Without a system of social constraints, the freedom of some actors can be violent for others, while security should be avoided.

Secondly, the security of any entrepreneur is to choose and choose the type of economic activity that he wants and purposefully.

Security as a precautionary measure for preventing and responding to incidents is a clear step in each individual case, depending on the nature of the enterprise, its location and importance. Security identification is important in this process. Its head of concern security development of certain production conditions should be personally involved in the development. [9]

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ASSESSMENT OF IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON LABOR MARKET AND HUMAN CAPITAL

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Abstract. In this article, the impact of artificial intelligence technologies on the development of the country's human capital and changes in the labor market is analyzed empirically and econometrically. The research was carried out on the basis of the sociological research method, and the questionnaire was prepared on the basis of the Likert scale. The validity and reliability of the survey options based on the Likert scale is based on the evaluation of its internal consistency. "Cronbach's alpha" coefficient was used to evaluate the internal consistency and reliability of internal consistency of the questionnaire using the IBM SPSS Statistics 22.0 program. As a result of the study, the result of testing the hypothesis that human capital has a positive effect on the state of digital development as a result of the impact of artificial intelligence on the labor market shows that there is a strong relationship between them. It has become clear that the impact of artificial intelligence on the education system can also directly affect the digital development of human capital in the country. It also became known that the healthcare system under the influence of artificial intelligence will have a positive effect on the digital development of human capital.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, digital development of human capital, labor market transformation.

Introduction. In today's "Industry 4.0" era, artificial intelligence can fundamentally change work processes. Another concern is that AI could have a negative impact on the labor market if human capital is not developed to accommodate the new changes. According to scientists, artificial intelligence has the potential to be "the most important general-purpose technology of the present and foreseeable future". However, there is also concern that advances in artificial intelligence could lead to mass automation and job losses.

The question of whether artificial intelligence will complement or replace

human labor is an important issue with policy implications. For example, if artificial intelligence replaces human labor, governments may reconsider retraining or digital skills training programs for affected individuals. On the other hand, if AI complements human labor and spurs growth, policymakers may instead support policies to encourage investment in AI.

The introduction of artificial intelligence creates gaps in human capital, which can deprive them of various opportunities and affect productivity. AI also creates the need for governments, organizations and higher education institutions to develop a national-level

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